

HORIZON-CL5-2023-D4-01 – GA 101138242

NEST InGrained ecosystem foR zEro EmissioN buildings

D1.5 – LivingLab activities

Document Information	
Due Date:	30 /09/2025
Actual Submission Date:	13/11/2025
Type of Deliverable:	Report
Dissemination Level:	Public
Prepared By:	Zeta Chrysafaki (PILI), Apostolos Mousourakis (PILI), Atsonios Ioannis (NTUA), Maria Founti (NTUA)
Version:	1.0

Disclaimer

This document's contents are not intended to replace the consultation of any applicable legal sources or the necessary advice of a legal expert, where appropriate. All information in this document is provided "as is" and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The user, therefore, uses the information at its sole risk and liability. For the avoidance of all doubts, the European Commission has no liability in respect of this document, which is merely representing the authors' view.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

1.	Executive summary	6
2.	Planned criteria (extract from DoA)	7
3.	Introduction	8
3.1	Purpose and scope of the document.....	8
3.2	Contributing partners	8
3.3	Relation to other activities in the project.....	9
4.	“LivingLab” activities	10
4.1	Aim and definition of “LivingLab”	10
4.2	Planning of the “LivingLab” activities	11
4.2.1	Inter-Partnership and social events planned by partners	11
4.2.2	End-users interaction with GreeNest ecosystem	17
4.2.3	Completed events up to M12	17
5.	Design of Light Clay Module (SP17)	18
5.1	Development of the Light Clay Module (LCMo)	18
5.2	The design of LCMo targets	18
5.3	Method of Design and Construction	19
5.3.1	Timber Frame and earth-straw mixture	19
5.3.2	Plaster and render	20
5.4	Laboratory testing	20
6.	Conclusions	23
7.	References	24

List of figures

Figure 1: Task 1.5 correlation with other tasks and WPs.....	9
Figure 2: The design of LCMo.....	19
Figure 3: The timber frame of LCMo.....	20
Figure 4: Preparation of the LCMo specimens.....	21
Figure 5: The construction of a wall with LCMo for the DC#7.....	22

List of tables

Table 1: Partner contributions.....	8
Table 2: Plan of LivingLab activities organized by partners.....	13
Table 3: General plan of social events & webinars.....	16
Table 4: Completed Social events up to M12.....	17
Table 5: Infill mixture of LCMo.....	21

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
LCMo	Light Clay Module
LC	Light Clay
SP	Standardized Packages

1. Executive summary

The GreenNest project develops, validates and promotes an integrated solution based on a digitized platform aiming to deliver a unified ecosystem comprising abiotic and biotic solutions approaching and facilitating a fast and extensive adoption of Zero Emission Buildings (ZeB).

Deliverable D1.5 “LivingLab activities” has been prepared in the frame of Task 1.5 “Social activities tailored to the local contexts to ensure acceptance - design of “LivingLab” (M6-M18). The “LivingLab” term is adapted to the particularities and aims of the GreenNest Project, to align with the overall aim of the project.

The “LivingLab” serves as a platform for active interaction between stakeholders and the GreenNest ecosystem, allowing participants to engage and, in some cases, provide data through IoT tools. A structured plan of events and workshops is implemented to promote collaboration among partners and engagement with external stakeholders

A review of the organization of social activities to contribute to the acceptance of the ecosystem and the preparation of the after-project interaction with the end users is presented in D1.5. Additionally, emphasis is given to the development of Light Clay Module (LCMo), made of rural waste and wood, for the practical experience of all stakeholders’ groups with an old construction technique planned to adopt ZeB criteria.

2. Planned criteria (extract from DoA)

Based on the Stakeholders Engagement Plan (T1.4), tailored social activities will be defined and organized to contribute to the acceptance of the ecosystem, securing social inclusion, justice and equity (“LivingLab”). In order to meet these objectives and based on the results of previous H2020 projects with successful results on users’ interaction (e.g. PLURAL, BuildinWood, NEST), a methodology will be developed for the involvement of end-users and key stakeholders who engaged in the day-to-day use of the buildings. The aim is to raise awareness on energy efficiency and circularity, ensuring broad acceptance of the GreeNest ecosystem. Examples of planned actions, designed with the support of the social task force, include co-design workshops with professionals, peer-learning, specific thematic-schools with workers, live/on line co-creation events with citizens and focus group studies in each demo case. PILI will contribute by developing a “light-clay building module” to be used in interactive training.

Outcome: Plan for LivingLab activities to enhance acceptance of the human-centered GreeNest ecosystem. (D1.5, M18). Additional outcome not foreseen in DoA: The upgrade of the “Light Clay Module” to SP17.

3. Introduction

3.1 Purpose and scope of the document

D1.5 presents the plan of the “LivingLab” activities that include: a) social events that will take place during the GreeNest project involving the Partners, b) the description of the LivingLab procedure that will take place after the completion of the project and involves the users of buildings where SPs of the project have been applied c) the philosophy, design and application of the “Light Clay Module (LCMo)” (SP17). It includes detailed tables with information about the events, drawings, sketches and the architectural description of the LCMo, as well as the preliminary results of the laboratory testing during the development of the material.

3.2 Contributing partners

Task 1.5 is led by PILIKO with contributions from other project partners. FENIX, NTUA, AMS, TUB, MPV are participating in this task, contributing to the list of Social Events, the method of LivingLab procedure and the construction of the LCMo, providing feedback for every different category. Table 1 indicates the contributions of each partner as initially planned, but also as arose during the collaboration in the program.

TABLE 1: PARTNER CONTRIBUTIONS

Partner	Contribution			
	Social Events	Living Lab	Light Clay Module	Other
PILIKO	Propose plan of events, planer, organizer, host, Dissemination	Method proposer and developer	Design, dissemination	Leader of Task, preparation of D1.5
FENIX	Dissemination		Dissemination	
NTUA	Planer, organizer, host	Method proposer	Consulting for statical behaviour, laboratory testing of building material of LCMo	Final review of D1.5
AMS		Method proposer		
TUB	Planer, organizer, host	End user of Demo site		
MPV		End user of Demo site		
MoS		End user of Demo site		
ZRS	Planer, organizer, host	Method proposer		

3.3 Relation to other activities in the project

Task 1.5 is closely interconnected with several activities across the GreenNest project (Figure 1). It builds upon the Stakeholders Engagement Plan of Task 1.4, which defines the key stakeholders for each demo and GreenNest SPs. The LivingLab activities plan, that are the main outcome of the tasks constitute critical inputs for Task 1.6, which follows and extends the work of Task 1.5, since the LivingLab assessment is carried out based on the developed plan. The social events defined in the current task will follow the Dissemination and Exploitation strategy defined in WP7. Last but not least, the Light clay Module that is designed and developed in the current task feeds Task 3.4 through the prototype development and testing of light clay.

FIGURE 1: TASK 1.5 CORRELATION WITH OTHER TASKS AND WPs.

4. “LivingLab” activities

Building upon the experience of previous European projects, such as PLURAL (<https://www.plural-renovation.eu/>) and REHOUSE (<https://rehouse-project.eu/>), the people-centred social engagement within GreeNest focuses on strengthening the acceptance of Zero emission Buildings (ZeB). This objective involves identifying both the technical and social needs of stakeholders and promoting the GreeNest solutions that address them. In the context of low-emission constructions, particularly those integrating innovative technologies, public understanding of the technical aspects is a key factor in achieving social acceptance [1]. Consequently, a complementary objective of the project is to enhance the energy and environmental awareness of users and professionals, enabling them to better comprehend, evaluate, and communicate their needs. This awareness serves as the foundation for the project’s participatory approach, which fosters collaboration between experts, stakeholders, and end-users.

To support this approach, a series of social activities (including workshops, seminars, conferences, and public presentations) targets professionals from the construction and energy sectors, researchers, policymakers, and citizens. Within these events, partners can disseminate the project’s results, demonstrate its innovative technical solutions, and promote active participation from a wide and diverse [2].

Within this framework, the “LivingLab” term is introduced as the central methodological tool for social engagement in GreeNest. It establishes a structured process of active interaction between stakeholders and the ecosystem, facilitating knowledge exchange, user participation, and collective learning throughout the project’s implementation. This open and inclusive form of engagement plays a crucial role in increasing awareness, understanding, and acceptance of the GreeNest ecosystem across different social and professional communities, as well as aiming at the enhancing of ecosystem’s performance.

4.1 Aim and definition of “LivingLab”

The term “LivingLab” refers to a process of active interaction between stakeholders and the ecosystem, during which participants may, in certain cases, provide data to the ecosystem’s Internet of Things (IoT) tools. This process aims to enhance users’ awareness and familiarity with the ecosystem, while also optimizing its overall performance.

Within the framework of the GreeNest project, the “LivingLab” constitutes a methodological framework designed to support:

- **Interaction among project partners**, through activities that foster knowledge exchange and collaboration throughout the project’s implementation;
- **Engagement between partners and stakeholders**, via social and outreach activities that facilitate direct dialogue with citizens, professionals, and policy-makers;

- **Involvement of end-users with the demonstration sites** (or other built environments where the project’s Specific Pilots are implemented), through actions that promote the uptake and practical application of the project’s outcomes beyond its official duration.

These forms of interaction encompass a wide range of activities aimed at enhancing mutual understanding—both among partners and their respective scientific disciplines, and between the consortium and various target citizen groups.

The primary objectives of the “LivingLab” activities are twofold:

- a) to familiarize stakeholders with the individual components of the project while simultaneously fostering a collaborative relationship among interdisciplinary partners, and
- b) to generate valuable insights into the real-world performance of the project’s standardized packages (SPs) within occupied, non-professional environments. At the same time, the initiative seeks to empower end-users by enhancing their understanding and control of indoor environmental conditions, particularly in relation to energy consumption and thermal comfort.

Within this framework, the “LivingLab” activities have been defined and organized, encompassing both social engagement actions and direct interaction between users and the built environment. A comprehensive plan for social events has also been developed. These events aim to:

- facilitate meaningful interaction between the project and its stakeholders,
- ensure the broad dissemination of project results, and
- promote public acceptance and recognition among diverse target audiences, including the academic community, professionals in design and construction, industry representatives, and policy-makers.

In addition, these activities contribute to the strengthening of cooperation and mutual understanding among project partners, while also promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and reinforcing connections between their respective fields of expertise.

The outcomes of the LivingLab activities are expected to have a lasting impact, extending beyond the official conclusion of the project. The knowledge and user experience gained through these activities are anticipated to support the broader adoption and optimization of the developed GreeNest solutions.

4.2 Planning of the “LivingLab” activities

4.2.1 Inter-Partnership and social events planned by partners

The events planned by the partners are categorized into two main types: those requiring physical presence and those conducted online. The formats and durations of these events vary as follows:

- **One-day lectures:** Typically lasting between 3 to 8 hours.
- **One-day workshops:** Also ranging from 3 to 8 hours in duration.

- **Multi-day workshops:** Spanning from 2 to 5 days, with daily sessions lasting 4 to 8 hours and consisting of both theoretical and practical training components.
- **Conferences:** Organized or attended by partners, generally lasting 1 to 2 days, with daily sessions of 4 to 8 hours.
- **Exhibitions:** Involving organization or participation, typically lasting one week.
- **Fairs:** Involving partner participation without specification of duration or organizational responsibility.
- **Webinars, meetings:** typically lasting 3-8 hours and happening among partners

These formats are selected to suit the objectives of each event and the intended engagement with all stakeholder groups that have been contacted in the previous reporting period.

All project partners have been requested to submit a schedule outlining the events they intend to organize, including the objectives and content of each proposed event. The majority of these events are planned to take place during the second, third, and fourth year of the project, corresponding to periods when more advanced experimental and operational results will be available.

The primary contributors, NTUA, PILI, ZRS, TUB, INEB, have prepared detailed programs of engagement activities. Their planned events primarily target the involvement of students, professionals in architectural and building design, representatives from local industry, members of the local community, and end users.

BIMETICA is contribution with a series of lectures aimed at training the project consortium members. The contribution of BGTec and AMS will be defined after the finalization of the construction activities of the demo sites in Greece and Italy.

Table 2 presents an overview of the social events planned by the project partners, detailing the type of event, the scheduled timeframe, the thematic content, and the corresponding stakeholder groups involved. This table remains dynamic and is continuously updated as new events are proposed and additional information and research-based knowledge are gained.

Additionally, online webinars organized informally by the project partners are conducted throughout the project to facilitate inter-partner interaction. These webinars are scheduled to occur between months 22 and 48 and serve to communicate periodically generated results from ongoing or completed tasks. Their purpose is to enhance mutual understanding of the scope and content of each partner's contributions

TABLE 2: PLAN OF LIVINGLAB ACTIVITIES ORGANIZED BY PARTNERS

PARTNER	1 DAY LECTURES	1 DAY WORKSHOP	MORE DAYS WORKSHOP	CONFERENCE	EXHIBITION	WHEN	AIM OF EVENT	WHERE	PERSON RESPONSIBLE	TUTORS	PARTICIPANTS
NTUA + KMAEL		X				13-17 OCTOBER 2025	DEMONSTRATION OF KARZ PRODUCT - ACADEMIC SOCIETY	NTUA	Olaf Elze (KMAEL)	Olaf Elze (KMAEL)	20
NTUA + PILI		X				MAY 2026	HANDS-ON WORKSHOP FOR THE PRODUCTION OF LCMo (SP17) LOCAL SOCIETY- STUDENTS- PROFESSIONALS	NTUA	Nik. Meimaroglou	PILI-NTUA	15
NTUA + PILI, ZRS, TUB, AMS, BGTcC			X			13-17 OCTOBER 2025 (SmartWall).	CO-ENGAGEMENT EVENT ON THE INSTALLATION OF Ecotech Wall, SmartWall AND ROTATING WINDOW AT NTUA SANDBOX ACADEMIC SOCIETY	NTUA		PILI-NTUA-ZRS-TUB-AMS	30
ZRS		X				DECEMBER 2024	TRAINING OF STUDENTS ON NATURE BASED MATERIALS BUILDING TECHNIQUES	NTUA LABORATORY	S.JANSEN / J.MOENIG / E.ROSWAG-KLINGE / A. KLINGE	PILIKO - ZRS - TUB - INEB - NTUA	25
	X					2025/2026	PUBLIC EVENT & GUIDED TOUR IN CONSTRUCTION SITE FOR TRAINING OF PROFESSIONALS, LOCAL INDUSTRY, ETC.	TUB	S. JANSEN / E. ROSWAG-KLINGE	TUB - ZRS - INEB	100
			X			AUGUST 2026	TRAINING OF USERS, STUDENTS AND PROFESSIONALS ON THE EARTH-SCREED - HANDS-ON CONSTRUCTION OF SP3 IN DC1 DEMONSTRATION OF BUILDING TECHNIQUE IN LOCAL SOCIETY	CONSTRUCTION SITE DC1	J.MOENIG / S.JANSEN / E.ROSWAG-KLINGE / A. KLINGE	INEB - TUB - ZRS	25

TUB		X			DECEMBER 2024	TRAINING OF STUDENTS ON NATURE BASED MATERIALS BUILDING TECHNIQUES	GREECE ATHENS - NTUA LABORATORY	S.JANSEN / J.MOENIG / E.ROSWAG-KLINGE / A.KLINGE	PILIKO - ZRS - TUB - INEB - NTUA	25
			X		JANUARY 2025	TRAINING OF STUDENTS ON WASTE-WOOD VALUE CHAINS & REUSE OF MATERIALS IN STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS AND COMPONENTS THROUGH EXPERIMENTAL PROTOTYPING	NBL LABORATORY (TUB)	S. JANSEN	TUB	5
				X	JUNE 2025	PRESENTATION OF DESIGNBYINVENTORY METHODOLOGY TO PROFESSIONALS ON SBE25 CONFERENCE	ETH ZURICH	S.JANSEN / J.MOENIG / E.ROSWAG-KLINGE / A.KLINGE	TUB / INEB	100
				X	JUNE 2025	PRESENTATION OF PREFABRICATED, CIRCULAR CEILING CONSTRUCTION TO PROFESSIONALS ON SBE25 CONFERENCE	ETH ZURICH	A. KLINGE / J.MOENIG / S.JANSEN / E.ROSWAG-KLINGE	INEB / TUB	100
	X				JUNE 2025	TRAINING OF STUDENTS ON CIRCULAR CONSTRUCTION METHODS - PUBLIC LECTURE SERIES	ZOOM: ONLINE LECTURE TUB	S. JANSEN / E. ROSWAG-KLINGE	TUB / INEB	100
			X		JULY 2025	TRAINING OF STUDENTS ON WASTE-WOOD VALUE CHAINS & WDLT-SLAB THROUGH EXPERIMENTAL PROTOTYPING	NBL LABORATORY (TUB)	S. JANSEN	TUB	10
	X				2025/2026	PUBLIC EVENT & GUIDED TOUR IN CONSTRUCTION SITE FOR TRAINING OF PROFESSIONALS, LOCAL INDUSTRY, ETC.	TUB	S. JANSEN / E. ROSWAG-KLINGE	TUB - ZRS - INEB	100
			X		AUGUST 2026	TRAINING OF USERS, STUDENTS AND PROFESSIONALS ON THE EARTH-SCREED - HANDS-ON CONSTRUCTION OF SP3 IN DC1 - DEMONSTRATION OF BUILDING TECHNIQUE IN LOCAL SOCIETY	CONSTRUCTION SITE DC1	J.MOENIG / S.JANSEN / E.ROSWAG-KLINGE / A.KLINGE	INEB - TUB - ZRS	25
	X				2026 & 2027	INCLUSION OF THE GREENEST RESULTS IN TRAINING PROGRAMMES FOR PROFESSIONALS ON WASTE-WOOD USE IN BUILDING PRACTICE, BUILDING TECHNIQUES, ELEMENTS	ZOOM: HYBRID EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMM BY THE CHAMBER OF ARCHITECTS FOR ARCHITECTS IN GERMANY	S. JANSEN / E. ROSWAG-KLINGE	TUB	100

AMS	X					2026	PUBLIC EVENT/GUIDED TOUR IN CONSTRUCTION SITE . Professionals, local industry, authorities etc.	Stypsi Demo Site-DC#4	CONSTANTINO S TSOUTIS/ MARIA SACHINI	AMS	50
PILIKO		X				DECEMBER 2024	TRAINING OF STUDENTS ON NATURE BASED MATERIALS BUILDING TECHNIQUES	GREECE ATHENS - NTUA LABORATORY	D.KADA	PILIKO - ZRS - TUB - NTUA	25
	X					DECEMBER 2025: 1 LECTURE EVERY WEEK "GREENEST TALKS"	DISSEMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT NATURE BASED MATERIAL BUILDINGS ALL STAKEHOLDERS	ONLINE	A MOUSOURAKIS	PARTNERS AND INTERNATIONALEX PERTS IN THE FIELD	100-150
	X					APRIL 2026: 1 LECTURE EVERY WEEK "GREENEST TALKS"	DISSEMINATION OF KNOWLEDGE ABOUT NATURE BASED MATERIAL BUILDINGS ALL STAKEHOLDERS	ONLINE	A MOUSOURAKIS	PARTNERS AND INTERNATIONALEX PERTS IN THE FIELD	
	X					DECEMBER 2026	TRAINING OF PROFESSIONALS ON THE LIGHT CLAY BUILDING TECHNIQUE - INTRODUCTION TO USE OF LIGHTCLAY MODULE IN BUILDINGS	GREECE CHANIA - TECHNICAL CHAMBER OF WEST CRETE	Z. CHRYSAFAKI	PILIKO	10
			X			DECEMBER 2026	TRAINING OF LOCAL MARKET/ WORKING GROUPS ON THE LIGHT CLAY BUILDING TECHNIQUE - 1ST LIGHT CLAY MODULE CONSTRUCTION	GREECE CHANIA - VEREKINTHOS ARTS AND CRAFTS VILLAGE OR ALTERNATIVE	D.KADA	PILIKO	50
				X	X	JULY 2027	HOSTING OF GREENEST GENERAL ASSEMBLY + DISSEMINATION IN LOCAL SOCIETY	GREECE CRETE - CHANIA CENTRE OF MEDITERRANEAN ARCHITECTURE (CAM)	A.MOUSOURAKIS - KATERINA VIENA	PILIKO	100
		X				JULY 2027	DEMONSTRATION OF LIGHT CLAY MODULE APPLICATION IN LOCAL SOCIETY	GREECE CRETE - CHANIA CENTRE OF MEDITERRANEAN ARCHITECTURE (CAM)	Z.CHRYSAFAKI	PILIKO	5

4.2.2 End-users interaction with GreeNest ecosystem

Withing the GreeNest project, four demo buildings will be constructed using the GreeNest ecosystem, integrating material, envelope and technical system solutions. Among these, the NestControl (SP16) will be installed in all demo buildings. NestControl will collect and provide data to the IoT-based digital GreeNest SPs (ASSESS-DST, SP6).

This system enables continuous monitoring of the occupants’ living environment and their interactions with the GreeNest SPs under various building uses and climate conditions. The collected data will be transmitted to the ASSESS platform for furthered processing, allowing real-time assessment of the overall building performance through specific KPIs (as introduced in D1.2).

In particular, sensors monitoring indoor air quality, thermal comfort and energy consumption will feed data into the ASSESS platform. The platform will evaluate the energy efficiency, comfort and environmental performance of GreeNest ecosystems. Based on these evaluations, the system can propose operational adjustments (such as controlling fan-coil units or window blinds) to enhance thermal comfort or reduce energy use, thereby maximizing the ecosystem’s performance.

Furthermore, the interaction between end-users and the GreeNest ecosystem, facilitated through the digital tools developed in WP2, will support a human-centred strategy that promotes continuous optimization of the ecosystem’s performance.

4.2.3 Completed events up to M12

As of September 2025, a total of 8 scheduled events has been successfully completed. Table 4 presents a summary of these activities.

TABLE 4: COMPLETED SOCIAL EVENTS UP TO M12.

Date	Event	Organizer	Number of participants
DECEMBER 2024	Hands-on workshop	NTUA - PILIKO	30
JANUARY 2025	Training of students on waste-wood value chains & reuse of materials in structural elements and components through experimental prototyping	ZRS - TUB - INEB	
JUNE 2025	Presentation of DesignByInventory methodology to professionals on SBE25 conference	ZRS - TUB - INEB	5
	Presentation of prefabricated, circular ceiling construction to professionals on SBE25 conference		
	Training of students on circular construction methods - public lecture series		>100
JULY 2025	Training of students on waste-wood value chains & WDLT-slab through experimental prototyping	ZRS - TUB - INEB	5

5. Design of Light Clay Module (SP17)

The Light Clay Module (LCMo) is a non-load bearing infill system designed to be applied within a timber frame structure. Piliko has developed this module, which can be constructed during hands-on workshops and training seminars in order to familiarize various social groups with the light-clay earthen building technique.

5.1 Development of the Light Clay Module (LCMo)

The Light Clay Module (LCMo) has been developed as part of the GreenNest project to support practical implementation and knowledge transfer within the LivingLab framework. Its development serves two main objectives:

1. To introduce a specific earthen construction material with clearly defined properties, which will be utilized during hands-on workshops with stakeholders. These workshops offer participants the opportunity to engage directly with natural building techniques and gain first-hand experience with sustainable materials.
2. To produce a preliminary design for a prefabricated construction element with low environmental impact, as assessed through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). This element is envisioned for potential application in future construction practices, contributing to the project's long-term legacy and alignment with sustainable building goals.

5.2 The design of LCMo targets

The LCMo design methodology is grounded in traditional construction practices in the mediterranean context involving light clay systems. These methods have been previously implemented on the island of Crete, offering valuable insights into the construction process at all stages. In the conventional application of light clay systems, a load-bearing timber frame is erected and infilled with a mixture of liquid earth and straw fibers, using a double-mold technique to form the walls. The resulting walls are subsequently rendered with lime-straw mixtures and finished with earthen plasters incorporating natural stabilizers. All construction activities are carried out directly on site.

The LCMo approach builds upon this traditional technique, targeting to advance beyond the limitations of conventional on-site construction. The objective is to develop a new building material that meets the following criteria:

1. Utilizes locally sourced earth and agricultural or rural waste materials
2. Can be standardized for widespread application
3. Possesses controlled physical and mechanical specifications
4. Allows for regulated manufacturing and application conditions

Through this approach, the LCMo system aspires to offer a range of benefits, including:

- A viable solution for construction in urban environments
- Suitability for dry-wall construction through prefabricated, specification-defined materials
- Simplification of on-site construction processes
- Enhancement of market accessibility and user confidence
- Promotion of local resource use and support for regional supply chains

5.3 Method of Design and Construction

The development of the LCMo creates a building element that can be adjusted in different timber structures, which is also easy to prepare and apply. The LCMo consist of two main systems: the timber framed filled with earth-straw mixture and the plaster and render coating at the both sides. Figure 2 illustrates the drawings from the design of LCMo.

FIGURE 2: THE DESIGN OF LCMO.

5.3.1 Timber Frame and earth-straw mixture

Natural wood is proposed to form a simple vertical structure with external dimensions of 50X250X25 cm, while the wood cross section is 40X40 cm. Several types of connections have been studied and evaluated

(Figure 3) and will be constructed during the hands-on workshops in order to inform the training material. The general principles are: construction simplicity, costs, mechanical resistance to wind and earthquake loads, connection with load bearing timber structure. The wood is treated with boiled linseed oil for protection from water, insects and mold.

FIGURE 3: THE TIMBER FRAME OF LCMO.

The dimensions of the module correspond to conventional Light Clay walls applied in real building projects in south Greece in Crete. The selected dimensions provide the optimal wall thickness for both satisfying thermal insulation and quick drying time. The filling of the light-clay mixture inside the timber structure is proposed to be done by placing the module horizontally and by using a metal grid so as to have a quicker drying procedure [3].

The earth straw mixture consists of liquid clayish earth (clay slip) and straw fibers. Laboratory testing has been done in order to determine the appropriate mixture. The mechanical, thermal and fire performance assessment of various mixtures will be reported in D3.4 (M22).

5.3.2 Plaster and render

Both lime and earth plasters have been studied in order to ensure protection of the earth-straw mixture of the LCMo. Two types of covering were investigated: a) direct application of lime-straw renders on the earth-straw mixture and b) a lime-earth slab placed with screws on the wooden structure of the LCMo. Laboratory testing has been carried out to optimize the LCMo performance in terms of the two systems.

5.4 Laboratory testing

Laboratory testing has been carried out on various mixtures of clay-rich earth and straw, using different soil types and varying amounts of straw fibers. The objective was to determine the optimal earth–straw composition to be used as infill for the LCMo, aiming to develop an industrial product that is both effective

and easy to apply. Figure 4 illustrate the preparation of the specimens used in the laboratory testing of the earth-straw mixtures. Table 5 shows the selected earth-straw mixture in this preliminary phase. This mixture will be applied in the LCMo during hands- on workshops with the stakeholders.

FIGURE 4: PREPARATION OF THE LCMo SPECIMENS

TABLE 5: INFILL MIXTURE OF LCMo

Earth	Straw (% by weight) over the total weight	Water	Density	Compressive strength (Fc)	Thermal conductivity (λ)
62.2%	5,2%	32.6%	926kg/m ³	0,59MPa	0.16 W/(m·K)

Figure 5 presents the design of a wall with LCMo, that can be potentially installed at the DC#7 NTUA Sandbox.

FIGURE 5: THE CONSTRUCTION OF A WALL WITH LCMo FOR THE DC#7.

6. Conclusions

The activities carried out under Task 1.5 have successfully set the foundation for stakeholder engagement and end-user interaction within the GreeNest project through the definition and implementation of the “LivingLab” framework. Building on the experience of previous H2020 project, such as PLURAL and REHOUSE, the LivingLab approach is designed as an effective methodology to connect technical innovation with social awareness, ensuring that the GreeNest ecosystem is both technologically advanced and human-centered.

The LivingLab is defined as a process of active interaction between stakeholders and the GreeNest ecosystem, where participants may also provide data to the project’s Internet of Things (IoT) tools. Its main goal is to help stakeholders understand the GreeNest ecosystem and to collect useful insights on its real-world performance. The knowledge gained from these activities will support the next phases of the project and help improve GreeNest solutions, ensuring that the ecosystem remains accessible, acceptable, and beneficial to everyone involved in the move toward sustainable and zero-emission buildings.

To achieve this, a structured plan of social and inter-partnership events and workshops (LivingLab activities) was created to encourage continuous collaboration among project partners and interaction with external stakeholders. By M21, eight LivingLab events had been successfully organized, showing strong participation from students, professionals, and community members in co-creation, knowledge sharing, and circular construction practices.

The ongoing development of IoT digital tools (ASSESS platform, WP2) is based on the real-time monitoring of end-user interaction with the ecosystem. This includes data on energy use, comfort, and environmental performance, with the goal of further improving the ecosystem’s efficiency and user experience.

Finally, as part of Task 1.5, PILIKO designed the Light Clay Module (LCMo - SP17) as a non-load-bearing infill system for timber frame structures. The design is inspired by traditional Mediterranean building techniques using light clay systems and supports hands-on learning through practical workshops that will be realized in the GreeNest “LivingLab”.

7. References

- [1] D1.1 - Analysis of Social innovation activities for retrofitting projects, REHOUSE - Renovation packagEs for HOlistic improvement of EU's bUildingS Efficiency, maximizing RES generation and cost-effectiveness, GA number 101079951.
- [2] FENIX (2024): "D9.5 - Awareness campaign report" of the HORIZON 2020 project PLURAL. EC Grant Agreement No. 958218, Brno, Czech Republic
- [3] Päätaalo J., Alao P.F., Rohumaa A., Kers J., Liblik J., Lylykangas K.- Prefab Light Clay-Timber Elements for Net Zero Whole-Life Carbon Buildings- *Corresponding author: kimmo.lylykangas@taltech.ee, <https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.sace.34.1.35561> - Tallinn University of Technology, School of Engineering, Department of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Estonia

